

Inter-Group Differences in Road-Traffic Crash Involvement

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Abstract

This paper assesses group differences in severe and fatal road-traffic accidents by using a unique database that merges road-traffic records with the Israeli census data. The database traces, over a period of nine years, a group of drivers that comprises 20% of the Israeli population and explores the probability of their being involved in an accident. This unique database enables the investigation of drivers' socioeconomic and demographic characteristics, while controlling for a variety of variables, such as estimated daily distance traveled and license type. Testing a previously published theoretical paper on the social bases of accidents, the findings expose significant group differences in estimated probabilities of being involved in severe and fatal accidents. For example, estimated probabilities of accident involvement are higher for males than for females, for non-Jewish drivers than for Jewish, and for drivers whose origins are in Africa and Asia than in America and Europe. Furthermore, the higher one's education and socioeconomic status, the lower is the probability of accident-involvement. The implications of the findings for developing road-safety programs and suggestions for future research are discussed.

Key words

Group differences; Sociology; Road-traffic accidents; Risk; Involvement probability; Socioeconomic characteristics.

1. Introduction

Over recent years, several road-safety scholars have emphasized the importance of social factors for road-traffic accidents (see, for example, Huguenin, 2005; Zaidel, 1992). As part of this line of research, Factor, Mahalel, and Yair (2007) recently developed a theoretical model for studying the influence of social and cultural characteristics on road-traffic accidents. The social-cultural (SC) model suggests that road-traffic accidents are embedded in the social context of driving. According to the SC model, the probability of an accident is influenced directly by environmental characteristics (road design, weather, vehicle type, etc.) and by drivers' behavior, but the model also suggests that the latter is influenced by individual and social-cultural characteristics.

The SC model builds on previous theory and research that suggest that social and cultural variables may influence action through shaping a behavioral repertoire, or "tool kit," that includes habits, skills, and styles that people employ to build "strategies of action" (Swidler, 1986, 2001); in this case, road-safety actions. Given that societies include diverse groups – ethnic and socioeconomic groups, for example (Blau, 1977; Clarke et al., 1997) – the nature of these "tool kits" varies greatly. Indeed, previous scholars have shown that every group has unique cultural traits, norms, behavioral expectations, life styles, and attitudes, all of which may play a part in forming heterogeneous encounters on the road.

Consequently, one may reasonably assume that the different social groups have different levels of risk-taking while driving and, consequently, different rates of involvement in road accidents. Studies in different disciplines conducted in a variety of countries and employing different methodologies support this argument and expose

significant group differences in a range of road-traffic areas – crash involvement (Norris et al., 2000), attitudes toward road safety (Yagil, 1999), seat-belt use (Shin et al., 1999), crossing against a red light (Retting and Williams, 1996), and speeding (Gabany et al., 1997), among others.

The goal of the present study is to test some elements of the SC model with the most robust sample currently available in the road-safety area. We show that road-traffic accidents are indeed socially distributed by revealing significant inter-group differences in involvement in severe and fatal motor vehicle accidents. Specifically, the paper explores the probability of drivers from different social groups being involved in road-traffic crashes within a period of nine years. This is done by using a unique database that merges road-accident records with census data, enabling us to trace the involvement of a representative group of drivers comprising 20% of the Israeli population. This unique database allowed us to explore group differences while controlling for demographic and socioeconomic variables, such as education and social class. Furthermore, the analyses were produced at the individual level and, except for daily travel, were not based on data aggregation or on drivers' self-report. The next section reviews current evidence for group differences in involvement in traffic accidents, focusing on gender, age, education, ethnicity, and socioeconomic background.

2. Review of Prior Studies

Gender has been identified as a significant factor in predicting road-traffic crashes (Yagil, 1999). Data from the United States (as of the 1980s) suggests that in almost every measure the rate of male involvement in accidents is double that of females. Furthermore, males incur more traffic violations than do females (Ferguson et al., 2001;

Taubman Ben-Ari et al., 2004). Men also tend to drive faster and keep less distance between vehicles than do women (Evans, 2004).

Age differences are similarly dramatic: the literature shows, for example, that road accidents constitute the principal cause of death of people between the ages of 15 and 29 (Sivak, 2002). It seems that young drivers possess an exaggerated sense of their driving ability, which apparently leads to a lower appreciation of the level of danger connected with different driving actions and, hence, to greater risk-taking behaviors while driving (DeJoy, 1992; Gabany et al., 1997).

Levels of education are also correlated with traffic accidents. Braver (2003) found higher mortality rates per unit of travel among persons with less education (even after controlling for reported seat-belt use). Furthermore, compliance with speed-limit regulations increased with increasing education (Hemenway and Solnick, 1993).

Similarly, other studies have pointed to the effect of ethnic differences in accounting for motor vehicle accidents. For example, some scholars reported a correlation between ethnic origin and driving violations, perception of risk, and road-accident involvement (Outcalt et al., 2003; Stiles and Grieshop, 1999; Vredenburg and Cohen, 1995). Low income per-capita has also been identified as a determinant of injury – the lower the socioeconomic status, the higher is the probability of being injured in a road accident (Braver, 2003; Zambon and Hasselberg, 2006). Shin, Hong, and Waldron (1999) showed that pupils from low social status schools buckled up significantly less than did those from higher-status schools. An exception to these overriding patterns was reported in a study that indicated that low-income drivers observed speed limits more than did drivers with high incomes (Shinar et al., 2001).

These inter-group differences bear testimony to the fact that different social groups have unique characteristics that include distinctive attitudes and behaviors while driving, and that these characteristics eventually might be reflected in different levels of involvement in road-traffic crashes (Factor et al., 2007). The literature further suggests that these group differences occur in a variety of nations; and it seems that the resulting inter-group differences tend for the most part to be similar.

Although much data has been collected on involvement in road-traffic crashes, studies that deal with socioeconomic attributes are apparently rare. In most cases, the effect of social position on road crashes – and this seems relevant to other variables, as well – was examined by an aggregative calculation of casualty or injury rates: total casualties or injuries among a specific class divided by the total population or sum of kilometers traveled by the same class (Lenguerrand et al., 2008); and the variables were not necessarily measured at the individual level. As one important scholar recently suggested, it seems that "in order to properly explore the effects of social position on the road safety of adult road users, information gathered among the whole road population is preferable" (Lenguerrand et al., 2008: 9). Moreover, there is a possibility that some of the above-mentioned studies found it difficult, mainly for methodological reasons, to distinguish among the effects of demographic and socioeconomic characteristics, such as ethnicity, socioeconomic status, gender, and education.

3. Methodology

3.1. Data

The study uses a unique database that merged Israeli road-accident records from 1996 to 2004 with the 1995 Israeli census and did so at the individual level by means of the

participants' national identification number (ID). The data was obtained from Israel's Central Bureau of Statistics after a committee that dealt with issues of confidentiality confirmed that there was no threat to the participants' privacy. The average link rate of the accident records with the census was about 92%. It seems that the failure to link 8% of the accident records was mainly due to errors in the ID numbers in the accident record or in the census data and to the fact that some of the drivers involved were new immigrants who did not participate in the census. In order to determine whether cases that were not matched resulted from systematic bias or from random error, a comparison was made of a series of variables (e.g., gender, year of birth, district where the accident occurred, whether the accident took place at night or in the daytime, road type, and more) between drivers who were linked to the census and those who were not. No meaningful differences could be found between the two groups.

The quality of the procedure was tested by comparing the gender and the year of birth of each driver involved in a car crash with the corresponding census data. Among drivers found in the 1995 census according to their ID number, there was about a 98% match (i.e., gender and age were identical), and the total percentage of partial (i.e., either gender or age was identical) and complete matches came to about 99.9%. The merging of road-accident records with census data facilitated an exploration of the social effects of the entire driver population over time and enabled us to conduct multivariate analyses that controlled for the effects of different intervening variables.

In order to estimate the probability of drivers' being involved in a road-traffic crash, we took only participants who filled out the "enlarged questionnaire" of the 1995 census and who, accordingly, represented a sample of 20% of the Israeli population. Then we selected only participants over 16 years old who had a driving license. For each driver

in the new census file who was involved in a road accident as a *driver* within a nine-year period (from 1996 to 2004), we next added the corresponding accident data from the road-accident records. If the driver was involved in more than one accident during that time frame, we chose only the first crash (during the period investigated, 11% of all drivers were involved in more than one accident, among them 2% in fatal accidents, 9% severe, and 89% light). In this manner, a type of "panel" data was created, with which one could examine all drivers who participated in the 1995 census, representing as mentioned about 20% of the Israeli population, and trace their involvement in road-traffic crashes over a period of nine years. Since the literature points out that road-traffic crash reports might be only partial in nature and even biased in regard to accident severity – severe injuries have a higher reporting rate, and the most reliable and complete data is that for fatal accidents (Elvik and Vaa, 2004; Evans, 2004; Hauer and Hakkert, 1988) – we decided in this paper to consider only fatal and severe accident data.

3.2. Socioeconomic measures

The present study uses three measures of socioeconomic status that are based on different definitions and variables – household social class, asset index, and mean family income per-capita (for an historical background and a detailed description of various socioeconomic measures, see Bollen et al., 2001; Oakes and Rossi, 2003). Social class was estimated by Erikson, Goldthorpe, and Portocarero's "Class Schema" (1979), which integrated occupation and personal status at work (employee, self-employed, self-employed with workers, etc.) into eleven class categories. First, personal social class was calculated for each driver from the census data according to the Yaish (2002) key file for linking class schema codes to the Israeli occupational classification.

Next, the driver's household social class was derived through Erikson's (1984) "Dominance Method." In order to create a hierarchical division, the categories were divided into three groups (Erikson and Goldthorpe, 1992: 45): "white collar" or "service class" (I+II), "blue collar" (III, IV*a-c*, V, VI), and "non-skilled workers" (VII*a*, VII*b*).

The asset index was obtained following a suggestion by Filmer and Pritchett (1999; 2001), who used principal components factor analysis to estimate the appropriate weights of the different variables in the index. The index contains 15 census variables that represent the housing characteristics and ownership of various assets (specifications may be obtained from the authors). The mean family income per-capita ("family income") was calculated from the original variable. The two last measures were divided into four quarters, the first quarter indicating low social status.

3.3. Exposure estimation

Annual mileage in kilometers is one of the strongest predictors of involvement in road-traffic crashes – the accident rate rises as the annual mileage grows (Lourens et al., 1999). Unfortunately the merged database does not include information about the drivers' level of exposure to risk (amount of driving); thus, we used a proxy measure in order to estimate this parameter.

The average distance traveled per day in kilometers ("traveled distance") was estimated in this research from the Israeli Travel Habits Survey, 1996/97. That survey's participants were divided into 52 groups according to gender, age, and district residence. For each group, a daily average distance traveled per driver was calculated by dividing a group's total distance traveled by the number of drivers in that group. These estimations were then merged into the research database according to the group to

which the driver belonged. The variation in the distance-traveled estimations within the subgroups was relatively low. The coefficient of variation $[(\sigma/\mu)*100]$ within each group ranges from 22.3% to 52.3%, with an average of 36.11% (for some validations of the estimation, see the Findings section below).

3.4. Statistical Model

In order to examine the relationship between socioeconomic and demographic characteristics and accident involvement and to estimate the probability of drivers from different social groups being involved in fatal and severe accidents within a nine-year period, a logistic regression was executed. The dependent variable indicated whether the driver had been involved in a fatal or severe accident within the past nine years (1) or not (0), and it included the following independent variables: gender (0=male, 1=female); three dummy variables for age (30-44, 45-49, 60+; omitted category=16-29); two dummy variables representing marital status (married, separated / widowed; omitted category=single); three dummy variables for years of schooling (0-11, 12, 13-14; omitted category=15+); two dummy variables for household social class (non-skilled worker, blue collar; omitted category=white collar); three dummy variables for asset-index quarterlies (omitted category=Q4); two dummy variables for work place (city of residence, city other than where the driver lives; omitted category=work at home / unemployed); three variables for the driver's religion (Jewish, Christian, Druze and other; omitted category=Moslem); four dummy variables for continent of origin (Israel, Asia, Africa, America; omitted category=Europe); estimated distance traveled; license type (0=other, 1= car only); interaction term between estimated distance traveled and license type.

The logistic regression was produced by means of listwise deletion, in which observations with missing data are omitted from the analysis (Allison, 2001). A few variables include missing cases (e.g., household social class, place of work), thus including them in the model caused a reduction in the number cases. A comparison between the attributes of drivers with "full" cases (i.e., without missing cases) (N=265,468) and those with missing cases not included in the regression (N=143,583) suggests that differences among the variables between the two sub-samples are not larger than 5%. However, there are a few more women (39% vs. 34%) and slightly more married (70% vs. 64%) drivers in the "full" sub-sample than in the sub-sample with missing cases.

To illustrate the findings of the regression and to explore the strength of the coefficients, we followed Pampel (2000: 29) and DeMaris (1995: 962) and transformed the regression coefficients into probabilities with Equation (1).

$$P_i = \frac{e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_p X_p}}{1 + e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_p X_p}} \quad (1)$$

We simply assigned the regression coefficients in Equation (1) and multiplied each of them by the corresponding sample mean. The category analyzed was multiplied by 0 or 1 (or another value), depending on the category being estimated. This interpretation represents net differences among categories, given that the other variables are set to their sample mean. Obviously, as was mentioned by Pampel (2000), given the non-linearity relationship between independent variables and probabilities, the effect of X on predicted probabilities will vary with the initial value of X. However, because the aim of these predictions is to illustrate average group differences rather than to obtain "accurate" probabilities, it seems that this kind of presentation is sufficient.

4. Findings

4.1. Comparison of drivers involved in accidents and those not involved

Of the 409,051 participants in the merged database, 4,486 drivers were involved in fatal and severe road accidents as *drivers* in the nine-year period examined. Hence, the average probability of any driver's being involved as a driver in a fatal or severe accident during that period, and based on frequencies, is about 1.1% (see Table 1).

(Insert Table 1 about here)

A comparison of drivers who were involved in accidents with those who were not involved, as shown in Table 1, produces an interesting picture. Apparently, some of the social groups are over-involved relative to their size in the driver population. For example, accident-involved drivers are on average younger, by age at census (34.6 years old), than are drivers not involved in an accident (37.9 years old). Jewish drivers (the majority group in Israel) are less involved (76%) than their relative size in the driver population (88%). However, Moslem drivers are involved in accidents at a rate (18%) that is more than twice their size in the driver population (8%). Participants who are involved in accidents have an average of 11.8 years of schooling, while those not involved have 12.5 years of schooling. Similarly, non-skilled workers are over-involved (26%) compared to their size in the population (17%). The mean monthly family income per-capita ("family income") in September 1995 terms is NIS 2,646 (about \$820) for accident-involved drivers, and NIS 3,216 (\$1,072) for those not involved.

Drivers with a license only for a car (66%) are less involved relative to their size in the driver population (83%). The estimated average daily distance traveled ("traveled distance") is higher for accident-involved drivers (50.95 km) than for those not involved

(43.27 km). These results reflect expected trends from the estimated distance traveled variable, since, as was mentioned, the accident rate was expected to increase as the distance traveled rose (Lourens et al., 1999). Moreover, when the distance traveled was calculated by license type, it was found that drivers with a license only for a car traveled less (41.7 km) than did drivers who held a license for other vehicle types (tractor, vehicle up to 15 tons, semi-trailer, taxi, bus, and so on – 51.1 km).

4.2. Probability of being involved in a traffic accident

Table 2 presents the model's logistic regression coefficients. As one can see, the model includes several variables that significantly distinguish between drivers who were involved in fatal and severe road accidents and those who were not – an unsurprising finding considering the large number of cases. For example, given the other control variables, the odds of involvement in a fatal and severe accident over a nine-year period are significantly lower for females than for males ($exp(\beta)=0.48$; $p=0.00$).

(Insert Table 2 about here)

(Insert Figure 1 about here)

Figure 1 shows the estimated probabilities of the different social groups being involved in a fatal or severe accident in the course of nine years as transformed from the regression coefficients (see above). The figure points out that the estimated involvement probability for males (1.09%), given other variables in the model set to their mean, is double that for females (0.52%) – even beyond differences in education, social class, religion, daily distance traveled, and so on.

Since in general males travel more than females do, it might be interesting to find out how daily travel correlates with differences in accident probability by gender. To do

this, we split the database into 20 sub-groups by gender and estimated daily distance traveled deciles (the ranges of each decile are presented in the figure). With Equation (1), probability estimations were then produced for each sub-group by multiplying the regression coefficients by their corresponding variable mean among the sub-groups. Because the second daily distance traveled decile did not contain any males, the two first deciles were merged. The result of this analysis, presented in Figure 2, shows that males' involvement probability is higher than females' in all daily travel deciles. Moreover, it seems that as the amount of daily travel increases, the accident-involvement probability rises. Apparently, the influence of mileage on accident involvement is greater for males than for females as seen by the steeper slope for males.

(Insert Figure 2 about here)

The probability of being involved in a fatal or severe accident decreases as the age at census increases, going from 1.00% for 16-29-year-olds to 0.64% among 60+ year-old drivers (Figure 1). Beyond differences that stem from other variables, the difference between the youngest group and the oldest group amounts to 56%. (A model that included age as a continuous variable and as a quadrate term indicated a slight increase in involvement probability for drivers over the age of 70.) Married drivers have the lowest probability (0.78%) of being involved in a fatal or severe accident, while separated and widowed have the highest (1.18%) – a gap of about 50%.

Involvement probability decreases as drivers' education level increases. Drivers with 0-11 years of schooling experience the highest level of risk (0.90%), and this percentage gradually decreases to 0.69% for drivers with 15 or more years of schooling. A similar trend can be found for household social class – the involvement probability of drivers who belong to the non-skilled-worker class is about 0.99%, while that of white-collar

drivers is about 0.75%. Just as in the education variable, the gap between the highest class and the lowest, when other variables are at their mean, is about 30%.

Accident probabilities also differ according to religion and ethnicity. The Druze and other drivers (1.27%) and the Moslems (1.19%) have the highest involvement probability within a period of nine years. Following them are Christian (0.94%) and lastly Jewish (0.79%) drivers. It seems that the estimated accident probability of Druze and other drivers is 1.6 times greater than the probability of Jews. The regression results show that among Jews, drivers whose origins are in Africa (0.89%) and Asia (0.85%) have the highest probability of being involved in a fatal and severe accident within nine years; they are followed by drivers of American origin (0.78%), Israeli-born drivers (0.77%), and drivers whose origins are in Europe (0.75%). Hence, when we controlled for different variables, the gap between the group with the lowest (Europe) and that with the highest (Africa) probability was 19%.

5. Discussion and Conclusions

The findings of the current research indicate significant group differences in the probability of being involved in severe and fatal accidents. For example, the involvement probability was found to be higher for males than for females, for younger than older drivers, for non-Jews than Jews, and for Jewish drivers of African and Asian origin than of American and European origin. Moreover, an association was found between drivers' socioeconomic status and involvement in road accidents – the more education and the higher a driver's socioeconomic status, the lower is the probability of involvement in a severe or fatal accident. Thus, similar to findings in other social and health fields (see Cubbin and Smith, 2002; Evans and Kantrowitz, 2002), it seems that underprivileged groups are the most vulnerable when it comes to driving. These results

were obtained from a logistic regression while controlling for a variety of factors, such as estimated daily distance traveled and license type. Though not reported here, we ran several validating analyses, and they have produced similar results. These further analyses, with diverse methods, included light accidents, discrete-time survival analysis, and an aggregative analysis of involvement rates per daily distance traveled and license-type owner.

The results as a whole emphasize the differences among social groups. Given different control variables, female drivers, drivers 60+ years old, and drivers with high levels of education have the lowest estimated probability of being involved in a fatal and severe accident within nine years. These groups might be defined as possessing a "social robustness" when it comes to accidents. On the other hand, Druze, Moslems, the separated and widowed, males, 16-29-year olds, non-skilled workers, and those with low levels of education have the highest probability of being involved in a fatal and severe accident – these groups could be defined as having "social proneness" to accidents. Hence, one can describe a continuum, on one end of which are located the "social robustness" groups and on the opposite end are placed the "social proneness" groups.

The results, therefore, support our position that beyond exposure differences, road-traffic accidents are unequally socially distributed and may also in part be socially generated. As was suggested by the SC model (Factor et al., 2007), the reason for these inter-group risk levels may stem from different group social-cultural characteristics. Different social groups have unique characteristics that include distinctive "tool kits" – habits, skills, and styles – that cause its members to interpret the environment and to make decisions in a particular manner. These particular group decisions and behaviors

might eventually be manifested in different risk-taking levels and, as a result, in different degrees of actual involvement in motor vehicle accidents.

The findings of the current paper reinforce previous studies that found similar trends (see, e.g., Braver, 2003; Ferguson et al., 2001; Outcalt et al., 2003; Zambon and Hasselberg, 2006). However, it seems that the main contributions of the current paper are its social and cultural approach to the phenomenon of road safety; the use of non-self-reported data (besides the distance traveled measure); and the large merged database at the individual level, which enabled controlling for a variety of variables.

One should, nevertheless, interpret this paper's findings and conclusions, though robust and comprehensive, with caution. Fortunately, the average probability of being involved in a fatal or severe road accident is relatively low. However, the drawback of these low probabilities is that the small numbers make it difficult to obtain accurate figures, and any small deviation, owing to different methodological problems, might cause significant changes in the findings.

Furthermore, although accident records were collected continuously from 1996 to 2004, census data was collected only in 1995. Using the census bureau's cross-sectional data makes it difficult to be precise in regard to drivers' personal attributes, because the exposure variable and some of the variables in the census file might change over the years (e.g., years of schooling, income, license type, and so forth). Nevertheless, that is apparently not a major problem, as most of the variables do not change dramatically over time. When, for instance, a comparison was made between the 1983 and 1995 census data, it was found that the average annual difference in years of schooling among participants present in both censuses was about 0.124 years ($s=0.183$); and in asset index, which is calculated in standard scores, the change was about 0.008 ($s=0.072$).

Moreover, when we repeated the above logistic regression analysis only for accidents that occurred within a period of three years from the census (1996-1998), and therefore the assumption of invariance would be more plausible, we found trends similar to the original analysis.

In light of the fact that we did not have mileage data for the census participants, we used a proxy measure to estimate drivers' daily travel level from the Israeli Travel Habits Survey. Though this estimation seems valid – according to a comparison of estimated daily travel between drivers involved and those not involved in an accident and according to license type – it might still be possible that more accurate data, and at the individual level (that is, not based on group averages), would lead to different findings.

The research model might also be improved if more exposure data were available in the merged database, such as characteristics of the roads on which the census participants traveled (inter-urban vs. urban roads), drivers' mileage on different road types and over the hours of the day, traffic volume at the locations where they drove, and more. Further improvements may be gained if we could incorporate into our model some individual road-traffic-related behavior variables, such as levels of drunk-driving or convictions for road offences.

Using the SC model and the results of the present research might prove fruitful in helping to develop tools to reduce traffic accidents. Since an accident is a rare event for the individual driver (Hakamies-Blomqvist, 2006) and since in most cases it is easier to change the perception of individuals through changes in the groups to which they belong (Cohen, 1970), it might prove advantageous to conduct social research and attempt to deal with the risk levels of social groups rather than to focus on the individual driver (see, also, Huguenin, 2005).

We propose to develop a variety of qualitative research studies in order to explore in-depth social and cultural mechanisms that could produce inter-groups differences at different risk levels and, at the same time, to divulge the causes of social "proneness" or "robustness" when it comes to involvement in motor vehicle accidents. For example, it might be possible to gain an understanding of the cultural "tool kit" of different social groups through in-depth interviews or focus groups. Scenarios representing different events while driving could be presented to the interviewees. From their reactions, it may be possible to learn about their attitudes, the reasons for their choosing different behaviors, and their decision-making process. In order to understand the actual behavior of different social groups, it might also be helpful to design a computerized simulation that would simulate driving in a variety of scenarios, including interactions between two drivers with the simultaneous use of two computers.

After the groups' particular socio-cultural characteristics are explored, it would be possible to develop, for example, customized intervention and prevention programs for school pupils that would focus on different socio-cultural groups. These programs would be tailored to each group, written with the aid of representatives of the particular group (Porter and England, 2000), and implemented in each group differently in order to fit the group's "tool kit." As Boyce and Geller (2002) advised, small behavioral changes while driving may save lives.

Tables

Table 1: Descriptive statistics for the main variables in the merged database, by involvement in road-traffic crashes

Variables	Not involved			Involved - fatal and severe		
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Fatal / severe accident (0=not involved)	0	0.00	0.00	4,486	1.00	0.00
Female (male=0)	152,530	0.38	0.48	680	0.15	0.36
Age	404,565	37.91	14.22	4,486	34.58	13.50
<i>Marital status</i>						
Single	108,336	0.27	0.44	1,560	0.35	0.48
Married	274,731	0.68	0.47	2,735	0.61	0.49
Separated / widowed	21,498	0.05	0.22	191	0.04	0.20
<i>Religion</i>						
Jew	355,722	0.88	0.33	3,410	0.76	0.43
Moslem	33,638	0.08	0.28	797	0.18	0.38
Christian	8,151	0.02	0.14	112	0.02	0.16
Other	7,054	0.02	0.13	167	0.04	0.19
<i>Continent of origin</i>						
Israel	96,048	0.24	0.43	1,522	0.34	0.47
Asia	83,048	0.21	0.40	874	0.19	0.40
Africa	71,830	0.18	0.38	898	0.20	0.40
Europe	139,891	0.35	0.48	1,106	0.25	0.43
America	13,748	0.03	0.18	86	0.02	0.14
Years of schooling	403,765	12.53	3.19	4,462	11.78	3.06
<i>Highest degree</i>						
No education / no diploma	27,262	0.07	0.25	392	0.09	0.28
Elementary / junior-high school	57,586	0.14	0.35	928	0.21	0.41
High-school / matriculation exam	178,780	0.45	0.50	2,058	0.47	0.50
Post high-school	58,257	0.15	0.35	521	0.12	0.32
B.A - Ph.D.	78,491	0.20	0.40	526	0.12	0.32
<i>Household social class</i>						
White collar	106,215	0.33	0.47	805	0.23	0.42
Blue collar	158,023	0.50	0.50	1,795	0.51	0.50
Non-skilled worker	52,932	0.17	0.37	892	0.26	0.44
Asset index	326,040	0.34	0.93	3,561	0.12	0.95
Family income	264,872	3,216.81	4,731.51	2,957	2645.75	2613.07
<i>Place of work</i>						
Home / unemployed	100,641	0.28	0.45	1,071	0.28	0.45
City of residence	116,867	0.33	0.47	1,211	0.31	0.46
Other city	133,910	0.37	0.48	1,578	0.40	0.49
License type (1=car)	404,565	0.83	0.38	4,486	0.66	0.47
Traveled distance	394,468	43.27	16.33	4,392	50.95	15.85

Table 2: Logistic regression of involvement in fatal and severe accidents on social and control variables

Variable	B	S.E	Partially standardized coefficients	Exp (B)	95.0% C.I. for Exp(B)		P-value
					Lower	Upper	
Gender (1=female)	-0.74	0.07	-0.36	0.48	0.42	0.55	0.00
<i>Age</i>							
30-44	-0.24	0.06	-0.12	0.78	0.70	0.88	0.00
45-59	-0.36	0.07	-0.15	0.70	0.61	0.80	0.00
60+	-0.45	0.11	-0.10	0.64	0.51	0.80	0.00
<i>Marital status</i>							
Married	-0.13	0.06	-0.06	0.88	0.78	0.98	0.03
Separated / widowed	0.29	0.11	0.06	1.34	1.07	1.68	0.01
<i>Years of schooling</i>							
0-11	0.27	0.07	0.11	1.31	1.14	1.49	0.00
12	0.25	0.06	0.12	1.29	1.14	1.45	0.00
13-14	0.18	0.07	0.06	1.20	1.04	1.38	0.01
<i>Household social class</i>							
Non-skilled worker	0.28	0.06	0.10	1.32	1.17	1.50	0.00
Blue collar	0.09	0.05	0.05	1.10	0.99	1.22	0.07
<i>Asset index</i>							
Q1	-0.11	0.07	-0.04	0.89	0.78	1.02	0.10
Q2	0.05	0.06	0.02	1.05	0.94	1.17	0.41
Q3	0.09	0.05	0.04	1.09	0.99	1.21	0.08
<i>Place of work</i>							
City of residence	0.02	0.06	0.01	1.02	0.91	1.15	0.71
Other city	0.06	0.06	0.03	1.06	0.95	1.18	0.31
<i>Religion</i>							
Jewish	-0.41	0.08	-0.13	0.66	0.56	0.77	0.00
Christian	-0.23	0.13	-0.03	0.79	0.62	1.02	0.07
Druze and other	0.07	0.13	0.01	1.07	0.83	1.37	0.59
<i>Continent of origin</i>							
Israel	0.07	0.07	0.03	1.07	0.94	1.22	0.31
Asia	0.14	0.06	0.06	1.15	1.02	1.29	0.02
Africa	0.20	0.06	0.07	1.22	1.08	1.37	0.00
America	0.04	0.13	0.01	1.04	0.81	1.33	0.78
Traveled distance	0.01	0.00	0.10	1.01	1.00	1.01	0.01
License type (1=car)	-0.99	0.16	-0.37	0.37	0.27	0.51	0.00
Traveled dist. × license type	0.01	0.00	0.19	1.01	1.00	1.01	0.00
Constant	-4.01	0.19		0.02			0.00

Figures

Figure 1: Estimations of the probability of being involved in a fatal and severe accident as a driver within nine years, for different social groups

Figure 2: Estimation of the probability of being involved in a fatal and severe accident as a driver within nine years, by gender and decile of estimated daily distance traveled

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